



A) What is orchestration load / what theoretical perspectives are there on orchestration load?

Yannis Ishari Korah



C) How can we measure orchestration load in different teaching and learning (in class, remote, hybrid) situations?

Alejandra Annelies



B) How different teaching modalities (in class, remote, hybrid) influence teachers' orchestration actions and orchestration load?

Davinia Anouschka

